

THERMOELECTRIC POWER GENERATION USING NON-BIODEGRADABLE WASTE

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ABSTRACT: The project is about the production of electricity by using waste. Researcher say one tone of waste can produce 500kwh of electricity. The project would help in cleaning the environment there by reducing land pollution and increasing electrical production in the nation. working mechanism is Thermoelectric Generator (TEG) modules to convert heat for burning waste into electricity. The hot side of the TEG is exposed to the fire. While the cold side is cooled using an aluminum pipe filled with water the temperature difference between the hot and cold side generates a DC voltage. This generated power is used to charge devices like cell phones, powers a 5V and energize high-glow LEDs. In this project, a complete energy generation and utilization system is designed and implemented using non-biodegradable waste. A waste-burning chamber is constructed where waste materials are incinerated to produce heat. Thermoelectric Generator (TEG) modules are installed to capture the thermal energy from the chamber. These modules are positioned to maintain a significant temperature difference between their hot and cold sides, ensuring efficient conversion of heat into DC electrical power. Multiple TEG modules are connected in series to achieve the required voltage output. The generated DC power is then passed through an inverter, which converts it into AC power (0– 230V). This AC output is used to energize various household electrical loads such as mobile phone chargers, fans, and a high-brightness LED lighting system. This unified system integrates power generation, conversion, and practical usage, demonstrating a sustainable approach to converting waste heat into usable electrical energy.

KEYWORDS: TEG, LED, WASTE, CHAMBER, MOBILE PHONE.

I.INTRODUCTION: The management of non-biodegradable waste has become a critical global challenge due to its long-lasting environmental impact and increasing accumulation. Materials such as plastics, electronic components, and synthetic polymers do not decompose naturally, leading to pollution of land, water, and air. Traditional waste management methods, such as landfilling and incineration, are not only inefficient but also contribute to secondary environmental

issues, including toxic emissions and greenhouse gases. To address these challenges, innovative solutions are needed that both manage waste and provide additional benefits to society. One such solution is the integration of thermoelectric power generation with the disposal of nonbiodegradable waste.

This process utilizes the energy contained in waste materials to generate electricity through the application of thermoelectric technology. Thermoelectric power generation is based on the Seebeck effect, a phenomenon where a temperature difference across a thermoelectric material induces the flow of electric current. By harnessing the heat produced from the controlled combustion, pyrolysis, or gasification of non-biodegradable waste, thermoelectric generators (TEGs) can efficiently convert heat into usable electricity. This approach not only reduces the volume of non-biodegradable waste but also addresses the growing global demand for sustainable energy. By transforming waste into a resource, thermoelectric power generation contributes to both waste reduction and renewable energy production, aligning with the principles of a circular economy.

II.LIRATRAURE SURVEY: [1]. Shubham Gupta, R.S. Mishra, "Estimation of electrical energy generation from waste to energy using incineration technology", *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovation*, Issue- 3, pp. 631-634, 2015. This paper mainly deals with viability of Waste to energy Incineration technology in Roorkee City, Uttarakhand by estimating the total municipal solid waste generated and evaluating the energy potential by using the incineration technology. Day to day increase in waste generation demands Renewable technology for solid waste management for an effective economic and social growth of the people. This paper focuses on technical feasibility only.

[2]. TR Ayodele, ASO Ogunjuyige, MA Alao, "Life cycle assessment of waste-to-energy (WtE) technologies for electricity generation using municipal solid waste", *Applied Energy*, Volume 201, pp.200-218, 2017. In this paper, life cycle assessment (LCA) of waste to energy (WtE) treatment plants for electricity generation in twelve selected cities of Nigeria is studied with the aim of evaluating their electricity generation potential, global warming potential (GWP), acidification potential (AP) and dioxin/furan emission potential. The benefits of the WtE plants are thereafter compared to the landfilling (waste management without intention of energy recovery) in each of the locations in order to determine the option that best fit the locations in an environmentally sustainable manner.

[3]. Samira Karimi, Barat Ghobadian, "Electric power generation from municipal solid waste: A techno- economical assessment under different scenarios in Iran", *Energy* 152, pp. 46-56, 2018. This paper deals with due to the increasing rate of municipal waste generation, Wasteto-Energy technologies for waste management have been noticed in the last two decades. The objective of the present study was to investigate and review the sensitivity analysis of different scenarios for choosing an effective and efficient technology using a gasification or incineration system from municipal solid waste in Iran. The challenge was to find the best suitable scenario according to economic aspects.

[4]. P.K.Mishra, Manoj Kumar Mondal, " Non-biodegradable polymeric waste pyrolysis for energy recovery " , *Heliyon* 5(8) ,2019. This article describes about Nowadays, increasing population, widespread urbanization, rise in living standards together with versatile use of polymers have caused non-biodegradable polymeric wastes affecting the environment a chronic global problem, simultaneously, the existing high energy demand in our society is a matter of great concern. Hence forth, this review article provides an insight into the technological approach of pyrolysis emphasizing catalytic pyrolysis for conversion of polymeric wastes into energy products and presents an alternative waste management technique.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

Fig. 1 Block diagram

1. **TEG Modules × 8:** Thermoelectric generators convert heat to electrical energy.
2. **Voltage Sensor:** Measures the voltage output from the TEG modules.
3. **Temperature Sensor:** Monitors the temperature to ensure the TEGs are operating efficiently and safely.
4. **Voltage Boost and Regulator:** Boosts and regulates the voltage from the TEGs to a stable level.
5. **Power Supply 5V:** Regulated 5V output to power the Arduino UNO and possibly other low-power components.
6. **Arduino UNO:** (Left) Collects sensor data (voltage and temperature). Sends data to an LCD display for real-time monitoring.
7. **Voltage Boost and Regulator:** Further boosts the 5V supply to a 12V power supply needed for higher power components.
8. **Power Supply:** 12V Used to power AC components via the MOSFET and transformer.

9. Arduino UNO (Right): Controls the switching of the MOSFET unit based on logic or thresholds. Can use sensor inputs from the left Arduino (via serial or I2C communication) to decide when to activate the load.

10. Mosfet: Unit Acts as a switch to control power flow to the transformer.

11. Transformer: Converts the 12V DC to appropriate levels for AC load.

12. AC Load: Bulb Final output device using the energy harvested by the TEG modules.

Fig. 2 Circuit diagram

The Arduino UNO in the given circuit is configured to interface with various components for a thermoelectric energy generation and control system. Two DS18B20 temperature sensors are connected to digital pins D2 and D3 of the Arduino, with each data line pulled up using a 4.7 kΩ resistor to ensure reliable communication. An I2C LCD display is used for output, connected via analog pins A4 (SDA) and A5 (SCL), while the Vcc and GND lines are powered from the Arduino's 5V and GND pins.

The system includes a bank of eight TEG (thermoelectric generator) modules, whose output is fed into a voltage step-up module and regulated to provide a steady 5V supply, which powers the Arduino through its Vin pin. A 3.7V battery and charge controller are used to maintain a consistent power source. For the control of an AC load (such as a bulb), the system uses a transformer driven by an H-bridge MOSFET configuration. The four MOSFETs in the H-bridge are controlled by digital pins D8, D9, D10, and D11 of the Arduino UNO, enabling bidirectional current through the transformer's primary winding. This setup allows the Arduino to effectively switch and control

AC power to the load based on conditions read from the sensors or predefined logic. The entire system may involve communication between two Arduino boards, possibly using software serial via unused digital or analog pins, although specific communication lines are not explicitly labeled in the diagram.

IV.HARDWARE RESULTS:

Fig. 3 Hardware setup

It incorporates various components such as an Arduino Uno, LCD display, voltage sensor, ice cube holder, TEG module, waste material burning sensor, cold temperature sensor, hot temperature sensor. Peltier devices are thermoelectric modules that deliver solid state heat-pumping for both cooling and heating. They also can be used to generate DC power, albeit with reduced efficiency. Where the arduino is also designed for the purpose of connecting the sensors which can find the voltage, heat temperature and cold temperature. These components work together to provide electricity by using non-biodegradable waste. Here the user can use renewable and sustainable source of energy and they can enhance energy efficiency by using waste heat.

DC VOLTAGE GENERATION

As we burned acrylic paper were burned, a DC voltage was produced. While we also tested other materials like regular paper and cloth, this case focuses specifically on the voltage generated by burning acrylic papers.

Fig. 4 LCD display before DC voltage generation

Here before the generation of DC voltage we can observe the hot temperature 30.7C and cold temperature 30.1C as present in room. The starting voltage before the generation is 0V.

Fig. 5 Generating electricity by burning waste materials

The generating process of electricity by burning non-biodegradable waste materials like carbon paper, plastic bags, cardboard, medical waste etc.,

Fig. 6 Generated DC voltage displayed in LCD display

Here after the generation of DC voltage we can observe the hot temperature 111.5C and cold temperature 8.9C. The voltage after the generation is 0.78V.

V.CONCLUSION: In conclusion, the project demonstrates an innovative and eco-friendly approach to waste management by converting waste into electricity using Thermoelectric Generator (TEG) modules. This system not only contributes to environmental cleanliness by reducing land pollution but also provides a sustainable solution for energy generation. By efficiently utilizing the heat from burning waste and converting it into usable DC and AC power, the project supports powering everyday devices such as cell phones, fans, and lighting systems, showcasing its potential for broader applications in renewable energy and environmental conservation.

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